

can be seen from the high positive correlation between seedling height and mature plant height, shortening of tall

traditional varieties by breeding can be expected to reduce seedling height. The Burmese variety D25-4 had good seed-

ling height while maintaining a relatively lower mature plant height. □

Flowering induction in photoperiod-sensitive rices which are potential donors of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) resistance

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Many traditional tall and photoperiod-sensitive rice varieties have genes for resistance to various stresses and can be used as donors. But their usefulness in breeding programs at higher latitudes is limited because they either do not flower or flower late and die of cold. With appropriate photoperiod treatments, such varieties could be induced to flower early and could be used in hybridization programs.

Balamawee, Ptb 19, ARC6624, ARC6579, ARC10464, ARC11321, and ARC11324 are potential donors of genes for resistance to WBPH (*Sogatella furcifera*), but they are photoperiod sensitive and do not flower at Pantnagar

Photoperiod response of different rice varieties at Pantnagar, India.

Variety	Days to flowering					
	70-d-old seedlings ^a		56-d-old seedlings ^b		Control ^c	
	10 h photoperiod	9 h photoperiod	10 h photoperiod	9h photoperiod	DS 28 May 82	DS 11 Jun 82
Balamawee	96	97	89	89	No flowering	No flowering
Ptb19	105	106	88	89	No flowering	No flowering
ARC6624	103	101	88	89	154	141
ARC6579	102	101	88	88	154	141
ARC10464	101	102	88	88	141	128
ARC11321	102	104	89	88	153	139
ARC11324	105	105	91	90	152	139

^a Sown 28 May 1982. ^b Sown 11 Jun 1982. ^c DS = direct seeded.

(29°N lat. and 79.3°E long.).

We tested artificial methods of flower induction. Varieties were planted 28 May and 11 Jun 1982. To induce flowering at 70 d for the first date and 56 d for the second, seedlings were placed in dark chambers for 10 and 9 h photoperiod treatment. One set of seedlings from each date of sowing also was transplanted in the field as a control.

When planted on 28 May, all varieties with 10 h photoperiod flowered in 96 to 105 d and those with 9 h photoperiod in 97 to 106 d (see table). When planted

11 Jun, the same varieties flowered in 88 to 91 d with 10 h photoperiod and 88 to 90 d with 9 photoperiod. In the field, flowering duration varied from 141 to 154 d in the May sowing and from 128 to 141 d in the June sowing. Balamawee and Ptb 19 did not flower in the field.

Flowering duration did not differ for 10 and 9 h photoperiod. Photoperiod cycles varied from 26 to 36 in the 28 May sowing and from 33 to 35 in the 11 Jun sowing. Fifty-six-d-old seedlings flowered earlier than 70-d-old ones. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Free-choice and no-choice seedling bulk tests for evaluating resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

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A free-choice seedling bulk test is routinely used for mass screening of rice germplasm to identify donors of resistance to rice leafhoppers and planthoppers. It is relatively simple, inexpensive, and fairly reliable when dealing

Table 1. Settling behavior^a of WBPH nymphs on seedlings of susceptible and resistant rice varieties in a free-choice screening test, IRRI, 1983.

Variety	Nymphs (%) that settled on seedlings at indicated h after infestation ^b			
	1	8	24	48
ADR52	4.2 a	6.2 cde	6.5 bc	6.0 c
ARC10239	4.5 a	6.3 cd	5.5 d	6.0 c
Colombo	4.5 a	5.8 de	6.4 cd	6.6 c
Muskhan 41	4.4 a	6.9 bc	7.1 bc	6.5 c
N22	4.4 a	7.1 bc	7.3 bc	6.5 c
N32	4.3 a	6.5 bcd	6.7 bc	5.9 c
IR2035-117-3	4.2 a	5.3 e	5.6 d	6.2 c
Podiwi A8	4.2 a	7.3 b	7.5 b	7.6 b
WC1240	4.1 a	6.6 bcd	6.3 cd	6.4 c
TN1 (susceptible check)	4.5 a	14.1 a	19.6 a	20.7 a

^a Percentage calculated on total number of insects released in a seedbox and remaining insects on the soil below the seedlings. ^b In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level; av of 5 replications, 750 nymphs/seedbox.

Table 2. Rice seedling resistance to infestation by WBPH nymphs in free-choice (FC) and no-choice (NC) tests^a, IRRI greenhouse, 1983.

Variety	Resistance rating ^b											
	18 Jul			25 Jul			31 Jul			8 Aug		
	FC	NC	Difference	FC	NC	Difference	FC	NC	Difference	FC	NC	Difference
ADR52	1.0	0.9	0.1 ns	0.8	1.1	-0.3ns	0.9	0.6	0.3 ns	1.0	0.6	0.4 ns
ARC10239	1.1	1.1	0.0 ns	1.1	1.1	0.0ns	1.1	0.6	0.5 ns	1.4	1.1	0.3 ns
Colombo	1.0	1.1	-0.1 ns	1.0	1.3	-0.3ns	1.4	1.0	0.4 ns	1.1	1.0	0.1 ns
IR2035-117-3	1.0	0.7	0.3 ns	0.7	0.7	0.0 ns	0.4	0.8	-0.4 ns	0.6	0.9	-0.3 ns
Muskhan 41	1.6	1.4	0.2 ns	1.2	0.6	0.6*	0.5	1.1	-0.6*	1.0	0.9	0.1 ns
N22	1.3	2.1	-0.8**	0.9	1.9	-1.0**	0.6	2.8	-2.2**	0.8	2.2	-1.4**
N32	1.4	1.1	0.3 ns	1.1	0.7	0.4ns	0.9	0.7	0.2 ns	1.0	1.3	-0.3 ns
Podiwi A8	3.3	6.0	-2.7**	2.5	4.6	-2.1**	2.0	6.5	-4.5**	2.6	7.8	-5.2**
WC1240	0.3	0.3	0.0 ns	0.3	0.3	0.0 ns	0.2	0.3	-0.1 ns	0.4	0.7	-0.3 ns
TN1 (check)	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns

^aAv of 5 replications. ns = not significant; *, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels. ^bScored on 0-9 scale: 0 = highly resistant, 9 = highly susceptible (1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice).

with highly susceptible and highly resistant germplasm.

However, shortly after seedlings are infested, nymphs tend to move to the susceptible check variety, which causes imbalance in the infestation on the test varieties. If this occurs to a significant extent, the escape of a test variety may be misconstrued as genetic resistance. We compared the reliability of WBPH resistance scores obtained in free-choice and no-choice tests.

In the free-choice test, 10 varieties were sown in 40-cm-long rows, each in 60- × 45- × 10-cm wooden trays in the greenhouse. One-week-old seedlings were thinned to 15/row and covered with a fine-mesh fiberglass screen cage 55 cm long, 40 cm wide, and 50 cm

high. Each seedling was infested with five second-instar nymphs. Nymphs that settled on rice seedlings were counted at 1, 8, 24, and 48 h after infestation. Seedling damage was scored when the susceptible check TN1 died. Treatments were replicated five times and repeated four times at weekly intervals.

In the no-choice test, varieties were sown and treated as in the free-choice test, but each row of seedlings was excluded from all others by a vertical, mylar plastic partition, assuring equal exposure to insect infestation.

The initial distribution of nymphs was uniform in the free-choice test, but after 8 h or longer, nymph percentages were significantly higher on TN1 than on resistant varieties (Table 1). This

differential infestation soon after insect release created an imbalance in the infestation level of the test varieties, which helped some resistant varieties to escape damage. This shortcoming was avoided in the no-choice test.

Podiwi A8, with *wbph 4* resistance gene, was moderately resistant in the free-choice test, but susceptible in the no-choice test (Table 2). N22, with *Wbph 1*, was resistant in the free-choice test, but moderately resistant in the no-choice test.

The no-choice test, which ensures even insect distribution on the test plants, may be particularly useful in screening of hybrid seed material for inheritance studies of insect resistance. □

Reaction of rice varieties to rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) infection by three brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes

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Recent screening data at IRRI indicated that the varieties resistant to RSV were also resistant to the vector BPH. We tested five RSV-resistant, two intermediate, and one susceptible rice varieties for resistance to three BPH biotypes and RSV infection in the greenhouse.

Varieties with resistance to BPH bio-

Reaction of 8 selected varieties to 3 BPH biotypes and RSV infection by those biotypes, IRRI.

Variety	Reaction to BPH ^a			Reaction to RSV ^b		
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Ptb 21	S	S	S	I (35)	S (76)	S (90)
Murungakayan	R	R	S	R (26)	R (31)	I (47)
Mawee	R	R	R	R (25)	R (22)	R (24)
Balaratawee	R	MR	S	R (13)	I (48)	S (70)
Hathili	R	R	MR	R (16)	I (40)	I (46)
IR22	S	S	S	I (58)	I (58)	S (90)
IR50	R	R	MR	R (21)	I (35)	I (33)
TN1	S	S	S	S (68)	S (82)	S (90)

^aData from Entomology Department, IRRI. ^bResults of mass inoculation based on 0-30% infection = R, 31-60% infection = I, 61-100% infection = S. Figures in parentheses are percentage infection.

type 1 in the mass inoculation were less preferred by the insect and received more insect probing punctures per day. When allowed to feed on resistant varieties, biotype 1 showed shorter life-span and

low nymphal survival. Fewer nymphs were produced by adults allowed to oviposit on resistant varieties.

Seven-d-old seedlings of the test varieties were transplanted in clay pots at 20